

Water quality modeling system for Lithuania

ID Nr.100054

USER MANUAL

UAB „Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment”
and SIA „Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs”

Client: Aplinkos Apsaugos Agentūra

Rīga - Vilnius, November - 2012

Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs

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“AZOTO IR FOSFORO BALANSO IR SUSILAIKYMŲ SKAIČIAVIMO METODIKŲ BEI PASIŪLYMŲ VANDENS TELKINIŲ APKROVOS TERŠALAIS SKAIČIAVIMO LIETUVOS METODIKAI PARENGIMAS BEI LIETUVOS SITUACIJOS PAGAL PARENGTAS METODIKAS ĮVERTINIMAS“ (PIRKIMO NR. 100054)

the Project is co-financed
by the EU

USER MANUAL OF MODELING SYSTEM

by

**UAB “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment” (ELLE)
and
SIA “Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs” (PAIC)**

November 2012

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1 Introduction

This is the technical user manual for the modeling system (model), developed by UAB „Estonian, Latvian and Lithuanian Environment” and SIA „Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs” within the project “*Development of methodics and modeling system of nitrogen and phosphorus load calculation for surface waters of Lithuania*”, ID 100054, see PAIC & ELLE (2012a, c, d). The draft of the manual was delivered along with the 1st interim report of the project PAIC & ELLE (2012a), while this – revised – manual is being delivered along with the final report PAIC & ELLE (2012d).

The modeling system described in this manual is developed, delivered and installed on the computer at Lithuanian Environment Protection Agency (EPA).

The manual describes the developed modeling system, necessary parameters, model preparation procedure and results of calibration.

The Chapters of this User manual describes:

1. The software components of the modeling system, needed for running the model and hardware requirements in Chapter 2.
2. The process and procedures for model data preparation in Chapter 3.
3. The structure of the modeling system, list and description of scripts for performing different operations, description of performing calculations and changing system configuration, calibration results in Chapter 4.

The sensitivity and uncertainty analysis sections presented in PAIC & ELLE (2012b) are excluded from the revised manual:

- The sensitivity analysis for certain set of parameters of particular SWAT setup (watershed) should be performed according to recommendations in SWAT CUP2 manual Abbaspour (2009). In PAIC & ELLE (2012a) the sensitivity analysis was performed for two - Graispis and Šušve setups.
- The uncertainty analysis for particular SWAT setup (watershed) should be performed according to recommendations in SWAT CUP2 manual Abbaspour (2009). In PAIC & ELLE (2012a) the uncertainty analysis was performed by SUFI-2 algorithm for two - Graispis and Šušve setups.

2 Software and hardware requirements

2.1. Software components

The developed modelling system is based on SWAT (Soil and Water Assessment Tool) model initially developed by Dr. J. Arnolds of Texas A&M University for USDA Agricultural Research Service. SWAT is an hydrology model with the following capacity of process description and functionality (components): weather data management, surface runoff, return flow, percolation, evapotranspiration, transmission losses, pond and reservoir storage, crop growth and irrigation, groundwater flow, reach routing, nutrient and pesticide loading, water transfer. SWAT can be considered a watershed hydrological transport model.

SWAT is a continuous time model that preferably operates on a daily time step at basin scale. SWAT uses a two-level disaggregation scheme; a preliminary subbasin identification based on topographic criteria, followed by further discretization using land use and soil type considerations. Areas with the same soil type, land use and slope of terrain form a Hydrologic Response Unit (HRU), a basic computational unit assumed to be homogeneous in the land cover / soil / slope properties.

SWAT modelling system and its development has been described in numerous scientific papers summarised in Gassman et al (2005) and it has rather comprehensive documentation (e.g. Neitsch et al (2002) for SWAT2005, Neitsch et al (2011) for SWAT2009, Winchell et al (2009) for ArcSWAT). The SWAT resources can be found in WWW at <http://swatmodel.tamu.edu/>.

The usage of the SWAT (and original) model components in the developed modeling system is illustrated in Figure 1. The model components are used to perform six basic tasks.

1. **Preparing of the model input data.** The preparation of the model input data (geospatial and other information) is performed outside the modelling system. It is described in Chapter 3 due to updates of the input data are essential for the successful use of the modeling system.
2. **Building of model setup.** Water quality modeling system for Lithuania consists of SWAT setups for particular watersheds which are organised in [regional] subgroups. The structure of the modeling system is described in Section 4.1 and predefined for the purposes of this project. Every one of such a SWAT setup contains multiple files with necessary input information. The Setups are created in subsequent steps:
 - a. **ArcSWAT** (Winchell et al (2009)) is a set of SWAT components embedded into ArcMap environment. ArcSWAT is modified by PAIC for the purposes of this project (see Section 2.2, p.1.b). It uses **ArcMap** geodatabase which can be processed by **MS Access** software. ArcSWAT and MS Access are used for the creation of **raw model setups** from the geospatial data and **ArcSWAT database** (which for the purposes of this project is extended with the records from the Harmonised world soil database, FAO (2009)). **ArcSWAT** is used for building model geometry and assigning meteorological data (see the description of data preparation and the raw setup creation in Sections 3.1-3.2):
 - i. subdivision of Lithuania into watersheds (setups),
 - ii. subdivision of each watershed into subbasins,

- iii. assigning reaches to each subbasin,
 - iv. subdivision of the subbasins into hydrological response units (HRU),
 - v. assigning meteorological data to HRUs.
- b. Automated scripts in Python language developed by PAIC are used to fill the geodatabases of each watershed with the relevant geospatial information, point source location and respective time series, reservoirs and their parameters, soil data, land use classes, atmospheric deposition, agricultural management praxis. Initial model setup is filled with default (process) parameters creating **initial model setups**. The Python scripts are listed and described in Section 4.3 while the data preparation and creating of initial setups are described in Section 3.3. The **Python language interpreter** is being installed along with ArcMAP software. The ArcMAP functions are enabled in Python language after installation of **pyODBC**. The **Microsoft data access object DAO** is required to enable Python scripts to perform geodatabase operation. DAO is a part of **MS Access** installation.

Figure 1. Scheme of information flow and components of the water quality modeling system.

3. **Calculation** of the time series for particular catchment or for the whole Lithuania.
 - a. Calculation is performed by numerical engine of **SWAT2009** (Neitsch et al (2011)) which produces result files from the ready-to-calculate setups. SWAT2009 is modified by PAIC for the purposes of this project (see Section 2.2, p.3).
 - b. The **system of batch files** is developed by PAIC enabling calculation of either single setup of the whole hierarchical modelling system (Section 4.4). Alternatively calculation management can be performed by PAIC SWAT software PAIC (2012) which itself is not a part of the WQMS.
4. **Visualisation and analysis** of the calculation results – time series for particular catchment of whole modelling system is further performed with external tools. The alternatives are either tools developed by SWAT community or PAIC SWAT software PAIC (2012).
5. **Model calibration and validation** is performed in PAIC & ELLE (2012a) and is not described in details within this manual. It may be performed by two independent routes:
 - a. As **autocalibration** of pre-defined set of parameters as a series of SWAT2009 runs managed by **SWAT CUP** (Abbaspour (2009)) optimisation engine.
 - b. As **expert calibration** via analysing of the calculation results and changing of the model parameters by **PAIC SWAT**, PAIC (2012).
6. **Modification of model setups** via changing input data or model (SWAT) parameters is possible for single setup, group of setups of the whole WQMS of Lithuania.
 - a. The **set of Python scripts** is developed for the application of changes in setups. In essence these are the scripts used for the model development in p.2.b, see their description in Section 4.3.
 - b. Alternatively the model parameters may be changed manually or via **PAIC SWAT** software, PAIC (2012).

2.2. Software requirements

Let us summarise the software requirements which – in general – are listed in Section 2.1. The principal requirements for the software components of the model system are as follows:

1. For the installation of ArcSWAT to perform building of raw model setups
 - a. **ArcMAP v.9.2 with service pack 6**
 - b. Modified **ArcSWAT v.2.1.6**
 - i. **Modified ArcSWAT.dll** file is supplied by PAIC. It allows writing "save" command instead of "saveconc" command to the .fig file. This allows the usage of ArcSWAT result files from one setup (downstream point of upstream basin) as an input files for another setup (upstream point of downstream basin).
 - ii. **Modified ArcSWAT database SWAT2005 2.mdb** file is supplied by PAIC. It is extended by soil records FAO (2009).
2. For the use of Python scripts for filling the raw model setups – creating the initial model setups:
 - a. **Python v.2.4**, installed along with ArcMAP v.9.2.
 - b. **pyODBC v.2.1.7** for enabling ArcMAP operations in Python.
 - c. Microsoft data access object **DAO v.3.6** installed along with Microsoft Access for enabling database operations from Python.
3. For performing calculations – **SWAT2009** – calculation engine used for the calculation of the model results according to setups prepared by ARCSWAT and Python scripts. The source code of **SWAT2009 rev.477** is modified by PAIC as follows (executable file **SWAT2009_PAIC.exe**; the respective modified source code is delivered electronically with appropriate comments):
 - a. File **routres.f** line 277, unmodified transfer of CBOD and DISOX through the reservoir was included. Originally CBOD un DISOX were set to 0 at the outflow.
 - b. File **hmeas.f** line 80, automatic detection of *relhum* for measured *relhum* data was turned off.
 - c. **watqual.f** from SWAT2005 version is used.
 - d. File **operatn.f** (lines 201-224), **readmgt.f** (lines 665-669): the scheduling of tillage operations by heat units are set as always based on the base zero heat units, independent of the plant growth.
4. For the use of Python scripts in the modification of the setups two alternative software sets may be used (i.e. developed Python scripts provides alternative use of these installations):

- a. Installation of **Python v.2.4** with **ArcMAP v.9.2**, **pyODBC v.2.1.7** and **DAO v.3.6** as in p.2 above.
- b. Installation of **Python v.2.6** with **ArcMAP v.10.0**, **pyODBC v.3.0.2** and **DAO v.3.6**.

Supplementary we may recommend installation and use of

1. **PAIC SWAT v.1.0** software PAIC (2012) for the management of the calculations, visualisation and analysis of calculation results, parameter studies, expert calibration and validation purposes.
2. **SWAT CUP** – for management of the autocalibration, uncertainty and sensitivity analysis via performing multiple (optimisation) runs of SWAT2009.

Working with SWAT one should account the following disagreement between the documentation and the executable files: wind data should be prepared for 10 m height (not 1,7 m as in the documentation).

2.3. Hardware requirements

The developed modelling system may be run on average to good Windows operated PC. Although the recommendations are dependent on the tasks and operation mode of the model system we may provide the following guidelines:

1. The recommended hardware requirements are CPU Core i7-2600K, 3.4Ghz, cache 8Mb, supports USB 3.0, HDD: 2Tb, SATA3, 7200rpm, RAM: 8Gb DDRAM III/1600Mhz, Case: ATX+ 750W LowNoise.
- The minimum hardware requirements are CPU Intel Core Duo 2.2GHz, HDD: 300Gb, 5400rpm, RAM: 3GB DDRAM.

3 Modeling data preparation and creating setups

3.1. Preparation of data for raw setups

The model input data was prepared for Years 2000-2010 in PAIC & ELLE (2012a). In this technical manual we provide more insight in the preparation procedures.

The raw setups were prepared by ArcSWAT. The data requirement for use of ArcSWAT are as follows:

- River network and subbasins
 - Digital elevation map
 - SWAT database file
 - Soil and land use grids
 - Weather station data
 - Point source data
1. The GIS layers of **subbasins** and **rivers** supplied by EPA were used for the watershed and subbasin delineation, and building of river network by ArcSWAT ("sub" and "rte" files).. Each of 1089 river catchments corresponds to one SWAT subbasin. The dbf files corresponding to the subbasin and reach shape files were modified to meet the ArcSWAT requirements:
 - a. Fields "Grid_code" and "Subbasin" have to be of long integer type in subbasin shape file.
 - b. The following requirements were checked and applied for reach shape file:
 - i. Field "ARCID" is of long integer type.
 - ii. Field "GRID_CODE" is of long integer type and corresponds to the value in subbasin shapefile.
 - iii. Field "FROM_NODE" is of long integer type and is the same as field "GRID_CODE".
 - iv. Field "TO_NODE" is of long integer type and corresponds to the GRID_CODE of the subbasin to which it flows.
 - v. Field "Subbasin" is the same as field "GRID_CODE".
 - vi. Field "SubbasinR" is the same as field "TO_NODE".
 2. The **DEM of Lithuania** was used as supplied by EPA.
 3. **ArcSWAT database** for the purposes of this project was extended with the records from the Harmonised world soil database, FAO (2009), see p.4.

4. The **soil data** was processed to create a raster covering the territory of Lithuania. It contains the predefined soil classes (from ArcSWAT database) and uses GRS_1980_Transverse_Mercator spatial reference. The supplied raw soil data was processed as follows:
 - a. The FAO classification code was assigned to all elements of Lithuanian soil coverage maps 1:10000 (*DirvDB10LT*). The FAO codes were acquired from (1) the respective records of database for unique soil codes, see the established relation in Table 1, (2) from the well database, (3) for the missing areas (forests) – from the LT soil coverage maps 1:3000000. 41 unique FAO classification codes were found.
 - b. The records from the HWSD FAO (2009) which correspond to the 41 unique soil code and the samples from Lithuanian territory were retrieved from HWSD by means of manual selection. The correspondence between the FAO codes and HWSD record number is given in Table 2. Each HWSD record contains the soil parameters listed in Table 3; they correspond to either the whole soil layer or 300 mm topsoil, or 700 mm subsoil.

Table 1. Established relation between the LT soil database (*DirvBB10LT*) and FAO soil codes.

Long FAO name	DirvDB10LT code	Generalized FAO code
S_FAO	SNS_KOM1	FAO
ABd-dyo	Jln2	Abd
ABd-dyo-el	Jln2-e1	Abd
ABd-gld-w	Jln-g0	Abd
ABd-gld-h	Jln-g1	Abd
ABe-euo	Jlb2	Abe
ABe-euo-el	Jlb2-e1	Abe
ABe-euo-em	Jlb2-e2	Abe
ABe-gld-w	Jlb-g0	Abe
ABe-gld-h	Jlb-g1	Abe
ABg-n-w-eu	Jlg4-b	ABg
ABg-n-w-fr	Jlg4-f	ABg
ABg-n-w-dy	Jlg4-n	ABg
ABg-n-h-eu	Jlg5-b	ABg
ABg-p-w-eu	Jlg8-b	ABg
ABg-p-w-dy	Jlg8-n	ABg
ABj-n-w-eu	Jlj2-b	ABj
ABj-n-w-dy	Jlj2-n	ABj
ABj-w-dy	Jlj6-n	ABj
ARb-euo	SDr-b2	ARb
ARb-dye	SDr-n1	ARb
ARc-ha	SDk-p	ARc
ARc-sk	SDk-z	ARc
ARg-n-w-eu	SDg4-b	ARg
ARg-n-w-eu-dl-sc	SDg4-b-w1-(s)	ARg
ARg-n-w-ca	SDg4-k	ARg

ARg-n-w-dy	SDg4-n	ARg
ARg-n-h-eu	SDg5-b	ARg
ARg-n-h-ca	SDg5-k	ARg
ARg-n-h-dy	SDg5-n	ARg
ARg-p-w-eu	SDg8-b	ARg
ARg-p-w-eu-dl-sc	SDg8-b-w1-(s)	ARg
ARg-p-w-ca	SDg8-k	ARg
ARg-p-w-dy	SDg8-n	ARg
ARh-eu	SDp-b	ARh
ARh-eu-em	SDp-b-e2	ARh
ARh-eu-gld-w	SDp-b-g0	ARh
ARh-eu-gld-h	SDp-b-g1	ARh
ARh-dy	SDp-n	ARh
ARh-dy-em	SDp-n-e2	ARh
ARh-dy-gld-w	SDp-n-g0	ARh
ARh-dy-gld-h	SDp-n-g1	ARh
ARh-pr	SDp-w2	ARh
CMc-p	RDk1	CMc
CMc-p-el	RDk1-e1	CMc
CMc-p-em	RDk1-e2	CMc
CMc-p-gld-w	RDk1-g0	CMc
CMc-p-gld-h	RDk1-g1	CMc
CMc-p-stn-w	RDk1-j2	CMc
CMc-n	RDk2	CMc
CMc-n-el	RDk2-e1	CMc
CMc-n-em	RDk2-e2	CMc
CMc-n-gld-w	RDk2-g0	CMc
CMc-n-gld-h	RDk2-g1	CMc
CMc-n-stn-w	RDk2-j2	CMc
CMc-fv	RDk-y	CMc
CMd-gld-w	RDn-g0	CMd
CMe-o	RDb2	CMe
CMe-o-el	RDb2-e1	CMe
CMe-o-em	RDb2-e2	CMe
CMe-gld-w	RDb-g0	CMe
CMe-gld-h	RDb-g1	CMe
CMe-stn-w	RDb-j2	CMe
CMe-fv	RDb-y	CMe
CMg-n-w-eu	RDg4-b	CMg
CMg-n-w-ca-p	RDg4-k1	CMg
CMg-n-w-ca-	RDg4-k2	CMg
CMg-n-w-fv	RDg4-y	CMg
CMg-n-h-ca-p	RDg5-k1	CMg
CMg-n-h-ca-n	RDg5-k2	CMg
CMg-n-h-fv	RDg5-y	CMg

CMg-p-w-eu	RDg8-b	CMg
CMg-p-w-c	RDg8-k	CMg
CMg-p-w-ca-n	RDg8-k1	CMg
CMg-p-w-ca-p	RDg8-k1	CMg
CMg-p-w-ca-n	RDg8-k2	CMg
CMg-p-w-dy	RDg8-n	CMg
CMg-p-w-fv	RDg8-y	CMg
FLc-gln-w	ADk-g4	FLc
FLc-gln-h	ADk-g5	FLc
FLc-ha	ADk-p	FLc
FLc-ar	ADk-s	FLc
FLc-fv	ADk-y	FLc
FLd-dye	ADn1	FLd
FLd-gln-w	ADn-g4	FLd
FLd-gln-h	ADn-g5	FLd
FLe-euo	ADb2	FLe
FLe-gln-w	ADb-g4	FLe
FLe-gln-h	ADb-g5	FLe
FLe-fv	ADb-y	FLe
FLm-ha	ADv-p	FLm
FLm-hib	ADv-u	FLm
FLu-ha	ADd-p	FLu
FLu-hib	ADd-u	FLu
GLd-dye	GLn1	GLd
GLd-ar	GLn-s	GLd
GLe-or	GLb2	GLe
GLe-ar	GLb-s	GLe
GLe-fv	GLb-y	GLe
GLk-p	GLk1	GLk
GLk-n	GLk2	GLk
GLk-cch	GLkc	GLk
GLk-ar	GLk-s	GLk
GLk-fv	GLk-y	GLk
GLm-cc	GLv-k	GLm
GLm-ha	GLv-p	GLm
GLm-ar	GLv-s	GLm
GLu-ha	GLd-p	GLu
GLu-ar	GLd-s	GLu
HSf-d	PDa2	HSf
HSf-tr-ph	PDt1	HSf
HSf-tr-d	PDt2	HSf
HSf-tr-d-ds	PDt2-(n)	HSf
HSs-ph	PDz1	HSs
HSs-ph-eh	PDz1-o	HSs
HSs-d	PDz2	HSs

HSs-d-ds	PDz2-(n)	HSs
HSs-d-ds-sc	PDz2-(n)-(s)-(r)	HSs
LPk	KDk	LPk
LPq-ha	KDc-p	LPq
LVg-n-w-cc	IDg4-k	LVg
LVg-n-w-dye	IDg4-n1	LVg
LVg-n-w-ha	IDg4-p	LVg
LVg-n-h-cc	IDg5-k	LVg
LVg-n-h-dye	IDg5-n1	LVg
LVg-n-h-ha	IDg5-p	LVg
LVg-p-w-cc	IDg8-k	LVg
LVg-p-w-dye	IDg8-n1	LVg
LVg-p-w-ha	IDg8-p	LVg
LVh	Idp	LVh
LVh-dyp	IDp-n1	LVh
LVh-dye-gld-w	IDp-n1-g0	LVh
LVh-dye-gld-h	IDp-n1-g1	LVh
LVh-or	IDp-t	LVh
LVh-or-el	IDp-t-e1	LVh
LVh-or-em	IDp-t-e2	LVh
LVh-gld-w	IDp-t-g0	LVh
LVh-gld-h	IDp-t-g1	LVh
LVj-n-w-cc	IDj2-k	LVj
LVj-n-w-dye	IDj2-n1	LVj
LVj-n-w-ha	IDj2-p	LVj
LVj-n-h-dye	IDj3-n1	LVj
LVj-n-h-ha	IDj3-p	LVj
LVj-w-cc	IDj6-k	LVj
LVj-w-dye	IDj6-n1	LVj
LVj-w-ha	IDj6-p	LVj
LVj-h-ha	IDj7-p	LVj
LVk-gld-w	IDk-g0	LVk
LVk-gld-h	IDk-g1	LVk
LVk-ha	IDk-p	LVk
LVk-ha-el	IDk-p-e1	LVk
LVk-ha-em	IDk-p-e2	LVk
PLd-dye	PLn1	PLd
PLd-fr	PLn-f	PLd
PLd-glp-w	PLn-g4	PLd
PLe-or	PLb2	PLe
PLe-glp-w	PLb-g4	PLe
PLm-ha	PLv-p	PLm
PLu-ha	PLd-p	PLu
PZf-gld-h	JDf-g1	PZf
PZg-n-w-or	JDg3-t	PZg

PZg-n-w-et	JDg4-ih	PZg
PZg-n-h-et	JDg5-ih	PZg
PZg-n-h-or	JDg5-t	PZg
PZg-p-w-cb	JDg8-h	PZg
PZg-p-w-or	JDg8-t	PZg
PZg-p-h-or	JDg9-t	PZg
PZh-or	JDp-t	PZh
RGc-ah	PRk-a	RGc
RGc-gln-w	PRk-g4	RGc
RGc-ha-es	PRk-p-(e3)	RGc
RGc-ha-ds	PRk-p-(n)	RGc
RGd-dye	PRn1-(n)	RGd
RGd-gln-w	PRn-g4	RGd
RGe-o	PRb2	RGe
RGe-o-es	PRb2-(e3)	RGe
RGe-o-ds	PRb2-(n)	RGe
RGe-ah	PRb-a	RGe
RGe-gln-w	PRb-g4	RGe

- c. The soil type related SWAT parameters (*Usersoil* table) were either directly acquired from HWSD, or determined by either SWAT or original methodics. The summary of the methods for the calculation of SWAT soil parameters is given in Table 4. Possible methods are: (1) numeric value, (2) variable from HWSD_DATA, (3) lookup table based on a variable from HWSD_DATA, (4) an equation dependent on HWSD_DATA variables for soil erodibility factor “KUSLE”. For the later method we used “Silt content” for “msilt”, “sand content” for “mvfs”, “clay content” for “mc”, “organic carbon content” for “orgC”, and used lookup Tables 7-8 for obtaining “csoilstr” and “cperm” from “texture class” and “drainage class”, respectively.
- d. The SWAT database was updated by these selected HWSD records.
- e. The shape and grid files covering the whole territory of Lithuania were created.

Table 2. Established relation between FAO soil codes (SoilName) and record numbers in HWSD (HWSDID).

SoilName	HWSDID								
AB	10400	CMc	10321	GLd	10408	LVg	10357	PZg	10414
ABd	10400	CMd	10321	GLe	10423	LVh	10348	PZh	10409
Abe	10400	CMe	10325	GLk	10419	LVj	10352	RGc	10577
ABg	10400	CMg	10333	GLm	10427	LVk	10341	RGd	8633
ABj	10400	FLc	10438	GLu	9125	PLd	10362	RGe	10454
ARb	10404	FLd	110	HSf	10435	PLe	10367		
Arc	10400	FLe	10441	HSs	10430	PLm	10367		
ARg	10407	FLm	10440	LPk	10357	PLu	10367		
ARh	10400	FLu	10441	LPq	10357	PZf	5108		

Table 3. Soil parameters from HWSD.

HWSD_DATA parameter	Description
DRAINAGE	Drainage class
T_TEXTURE	Texture class
AWC_CLASS	Available water capacity class
T_REF_BULK_DENSITY	Topsoil bulk density, g/cm ³
T_OC	Topsoil organic carbon content, %
T_CLAY	Topsoil clay content, %
T_SILT	Topsoil silt content, %
T_SAND	Topsoil sand content, %
T_GRAVEL	Topsoil gravel content, %
T_ECE	Topsoil electrical conductivity, dS/m
s_REF_BULK_DENSITY	Subsoil bulk density, g/cm ³
s_OC	Subsoil organic carbon content, %
s_CLAY	Subsoil clay content, %
s_SILT	Subsoil silt content, %
s_SAND	Subsoil sand content, %
s_GRAVEL	Subsoil gravel content, %
S_ECE	Subsoil electrical conductivity, dS/m

Table 4. The variables of ArcSWAT *usersoil* table and method of their calculation.

Usersoil abbreviation	Name	Method
NLAYERS	Number of soil layers	2
HYDGRP	Soil hydrological group	Lookup based on DRAINAGE (Table 5)
SOL_ZMX	Maximum rooting depth of profile, mm	1000
ANION_EXCL	Fraction of porosity from which anions are excluded	0.5
SOL_CRK	Crack volume potential of soil	0.5
SOL_Z1	Depth to bottom of the first soil layer, mm	300
SOL_BD1	Moist bulk density of first soil layer, Mg/m ³	=T_REF_BULK_DENSITY
SOL_AWC1	Available water capacity of first soil layer, mm H ₂ O/mm soil	Lookup based on AWC_CLASS (Table 6)
SOL_K1	Saturated hydraulic conductivity of first soil layer, mm/hr	Lookup based on HYDGRP (Table 5)
SOL_CBN1	Organic carbon content of first soil layer, %	=T_OC
CLAY1	Clay content of first soil layer, %	=T_CLAY
SILT1	Silt content of first soil layer, %	=T_SILT
SAND1	Sand content of first soil layer, %	=T_SAND
ROCK1	Rock content of first soil layer, %	=T_GRAVEL
SOL_ALB1	Moist soil albedo of first soil layer	0.09
USLE_K1	USLE equation soil erodibility factor of first soil layer	Equations 4:1.1.2-4:1.1.4 of SWAT 2005 documentation Neitsch et al (2002)

SOL_EC1	Electrical conductivity of first soil layer	=T_ECE
SOL_Z2	Depth to bottom of the second soil layer, mm	1000
SOL_BD2	Moist bulk density of second soil layer, Mg/m ³	=S_REF_BULK_DENSITY
SOL_AWC2	Available water capacity of second soil layer, mm H ₂ O/mm soil	Lookup based on AWC_CLASS (Table 6)
SOL_K2	Saturated hydraulic conductivity of second soil layer, mm/hr	Lookup based on HYDGRP (Table 5)
SOL_CBN2	Organic carbon content of second soil layer, %	=S_OC
CLAY2	Clay content of second soil layer, %	=S_CLAY
SILT2	Silt content of second soil layer, %	=S_SILT
SAND2	Sand content of second soil layer, %	=S_SAND
ROCK2	Rock content of second soil layer, %	=S_GRAVEL
SOL_ALB2	Moist soil albedo of second soil layer	0.09
USLE_K2	USLE equation soil erodibility factor of second soil layer	Equations 4:1.1.2-4:1.1.4 of SWAT 2005 documentation Neitsch et al (2002)
SOL_EC2	Electrical conductivity of second soil layer	=S_ECE

Table 5. Lookup table relating drainage class and soil hydrological group.

HWSD drainage class	HWSD drainage class name	Soil hydrological group	Saturated hydraulic conductivity, mm/hr
1	Very Poor	D	2
2	Poor	C	5
3	Imperfectly	C	5
4	Moderately Well	B	20
5	Well	B	20
6	Somewhat Excessive	A	50
7	Excessive	A	50

Table 6. Lookup table relating AWC class and SOL_AWC values.

AWC_CLASS	SOL_AWC
1	0.15
2	0.125
3	0.1
4	0.075
5	0.05
6	0.015
7	0

- The **land use data** was processed to create a raster covering the territory of Lithuania. It contains the predefined land use classes (from ArcSWAT database) and uses GRS_1980_Transverse_Mercator spatial reference. The supplied land use data was processed as follows:

Table 7. Lookup table relating HWSD texture class with *csoilstr* used in equation for calculating of *USLE_K*.

HWSD texture class	HWSD texture class name	<i>csoilstr</i>	<i>csoilstr</i> name, SWAT 2005 documentation Neitsch et al (2002), p.228
1	Coarse	3	Medium or coarse granular
2	Medium	2	Fine granular
3	Fine	1	Very fine granular

Table 8. Lookup table relating HWSD drainage class with *cperm* used in equation for calculating of *USLE_K*.

:HWSD drainage class	HWSD drainage class name	<i>Cperm</i>	<i>cperm</i> name, SWAT 2005 documentation Neitsch et al (2002), p.228
1	Very Poor	6	Very slow
2	Poor	5	Slow
3	Imperfectly	4	Slow to moderate
4	Moderately Well	3	Moderate
5	Well	2	Moderate to rapid
6	Somewhat Excessive	1	Rapid
7	Excessive	1	Rapid

- a. The declared **land use** was available for the agricultural land of Lithuania. The Corine land cover database was used for the rest of the territory.
 - b. The following steps were performed to assign 41 unique ArcSWAT land use identifier (corresponding to a particular crop) to particular land use polygon of initial data; additionally all land uses were divided (generalised into 5 groups (agricultural, pastures, forests, urban and water) for applying different SWAT management praxis algorithms:
 - i. The declared crops were translated to English and assigned to agricultural ArcSWAT land use classes. The correspondence of the declared land use (field “PSL_PAVAD”) and SWAT code is submitted electronically (file **CROPS_LT_SWAT.XLSX**) The declared territories included also pastures and apple-gardens (see Table 9).
 - ii. The ArcSWAT land use for the rest of the territory was assigned according to CORINE classification, see corresponding codes in Table 9. WETF and WETN land use types were applied for the calculation of the wetland fraction of each subbasin.
 - c. The shape and grid files of the land use were prepared by ArcMap
6. Unique combinations of the soil type (p.4) and the land use (p.5) are a basis for distinguishing **hydrological response units** (HRU) within each subbasin. “hru” files were generated by ArcSWAT, see Section 3.2, pp. 4-5.

Table 9. ARCSWAT land use (crop) classes, source of classification and corresponding CORINE codes and classes.

ARCSWAT land use code	Land use type	Source of classification	Corine code: class
AGR, ALFA, BARL, CANP, CORN, CRRT, EGGP, FESC, FLAX, FPEA, GRBN, LENT, OATS, PEAS, POTA, RYE, SCR, SGBT, SOYB, STRW, SWHT, TIMO, TOMA, WWHT	Agricultural	Declared land use	N/A
ORCD	Agricultural	CORINE, declared land use	222: Fruit trees and berry plantations
AGRC	Agricultural	CORINE, declared land use	211: Non-irrigated arable land, 242: Complex cultivation patterns
BROM, CLVR	Pastures	Declared land use	N/A
RYEG	Pastures	CORINE	321: Natural grasslands, 322: Moors and heathland
WPAS	Pastures	CORINE	231: Pastures
APPL	Forest	Declared land use	N/A
FRSD	Forest	CORINE	324: Transitional woodland-scrub, 333: Sparsely vegetated areas
FRSE	Forest	CORINE	312: Coniferous forest
FRST	Forest	CORINE	311: Broad-leaved forest, 313: Mixed forest
WETF	Forest	CORINE	411: Inland marshes, 412: Peat bogs
UIDU	Urban	CORINE	121: Industrial or commercial, 122: Road and rail network and associated land, 123: Port areas, 124: Airports
URHD	Urban	CORINE	111: Continuous urban fabric
URLD	Urban	CORINE	131: Mineral extraction sites, 132: Dump sites, 133: Construction sites, 141: Green urban areas, 142: Sport and leisure facilities
URML	Urban	CORINE	112: Discont. urban fabric
WATR	Water	CORINE	511: Water courses, 512: Water bodies, 521: coastal lagoons
WETN	Water	CORINE	331: Beaches, dunes and sand plains

7. SWAT requires daily **meteorological data series** (separate databases of precipitation, air temperature [min and max values], wind velocity, humidity and solar radiation). The hourly meteorological data was used for determining daily temperature extremes. The following data preprocessing was done:
 - a. The lists of meteorological stations (see the location in Fig. 2) and their coordinates were created separately for each of meteorological data types – weather generator data **meteostc.dbf**, rainfall data **pcplist.dbf**, temperature data **tmplist.dbf**, relative humidity data **hmdlist.dbf**, solar radiation data **sollist.dbf**, and wind speed data **wndlist.dbf**.
 - b. The daily values of the meteorological dataset was used to produce meteorological data files for each station (**wgnXX.dbf**, **pcpXX.dbf**, **tmpXX**, **hmdXX.dbf**, **slrXX.dbf**, **wndXX.dbf**). Here file names must correspond to the station name in the list of meteorological station of given type (i.e. database of p.7a). The weather generator file "wgn" is only formally needed for running the ArcSWAT; weather generator was not used due to the availability of continuous observation data for the time period used further in the calculations.
 - c. The meteorological databases were further linked to raw setups (see Section 3.2, p.6) and additionally processed (including correction of the precipitation distribution) in transition from the raw to initial setups, see Section 3.3, p.8.

Fig. 2. Meteorological stations, precipitation stations, and mean annual precipitation assigned for each of the subbasins.

3.2. Creation of raw setups

The steps needed for the creating of a single raw setup are as follows:

1. **Starting new project** includes sequential operations (1) Opening ArcMAP, (2) adding ArcSWAT extension. (3) clicking "New SWAT Project", see Fig. 3. Such operations must be performed for each of the setups.

Fig. 3. Starting new ArcSWAT project.

Fig. 4. Defining setup directory and specifying ArcSWAT database.

2. Defining the **setup directory** and specifying the **SWAT database** for particular setup (Fig. 4).
3. Creation of **subbasins and the river network** (including adding dummy **point sources**) includes the following actions:

Fig. 5. Starting of watershed delineation.

Fig. 6. Steps of watershed delineation.

- a. Opening the “Watershed delineation” tool (Fig. 5) and performing the further actions (see Fig. 6).
- b. Choosing the DEM file.
- c. Selecting “Pre-defined streams” and specifying the input data – shape files of subbasins and reaches.
- d. Specifying the presence of point source in the actual subbasin.
- e. Pressing button “Calculate subbasin parameters”.

4. **Soil, land use and slope** definition for a particular setup is started by respective selection from pull-down menu (Fig. 7) after opening the grid attribute tables and **landuse_lookup.xls**.

Fig. 7. Start of soil, land use and slope definition for particular setup.

- a. Definition of the land use involves the following actions (Fig. 8).
 - i. Specification of the land use grid file (it must cover at least 95% of the subbasin area).
 - ii. Choosing Grid Field "VALUE"
 - iii. Specifying the SWAT land use values via look-up table **lookup_landuse.xls**.
 - iv. Pressing button "Reclassify".
- b. Definition of the soil data involves the following actions (Fig. 9).
 - i. Specification of the soils grid file (it must cover at least 95% of the subbasin area).
 - ii. Choosing Grid Field "VALUE" and soil specification Option "Name".
 - iii. Specifying the SWAT soil type values.
 - iv. Pressing button "Reclassify".

- c. The HRUs are not distinguished by slope in the prepared modelling system (the reason for this is the reduction of the calculation time). Application of the single slope HRU is performed via selection of "Slope Discretization = Single Slope" and pressing button "Reclassify", see Fig. 10.

Fig. 8. Definition of Land use.

Fig. 9. Definition of Soil data.

Fig. 10. Specification of single slope HRUs.

5. Creating of **HRUs** of the particular setup involves the following steps:
 - a. Selecting "Create HRU Feature Class" and pressing button "Overlay" in "Land use / Soils / Slope Definition" window, see Fig. 11. This operation creates a "Full_HRU" ArcMap layer, see Fig.12.
 - b. Invoking the HRU definition procedure from pull-down menu (Fig.13).

Fig.11. Overlaying Land use / Soils / Slope for creating Full_HRU ArcMAP layer.

Fig. 12. Example of Full_HRU layer.

- c. Applying HRU definition parameters in the HRU definition window (Fig.14): (1) specifying HRU threshold "Area", (2) selecting appropriate threshold values for land use and soil type, (3) pressing button "Create HRUs".
- d. The summary report of HRU definition can be reviewed, see Fig. 15.

Fig.13. Invoking HRU definition dialogue.

Fig. 14. HRU definition window.

SWAT model simulation Date: 2012.09.12. 0:00:00 Time: 00:00:00
 MULTIPLE HRUs LandUse/Soil/Slope OPTION THRESHOLDS : 100 / 100 / 100 [ha]
 Number of HRUs: 314
 Number of Subbasins: 17

watershed	Area [ha]	Area[acres]
watershed	122771.0600	303373.4279

LANDUSE:	Area [ha]	Area[acres]	%wat.Area
Agricultural Land-Close-grown --> AGRC	53388.6567	131926.0401	43.49
winter Pasture --> WPAS	6190.2184	15296.3392	5.04
Spring Barley --> BARL	2546.0815	6291.4948	2.07
Forest-Evergreen --> FRSE	18609.6318	45985.3307	15.16
spring Canola-Polish --> CANP	1466.2379	3623.1472	1.19
winter wheat --> WWHT	2884.4557	7127.6342	2.35
Forest-Mixed --> FRST	25490.4625	62988.2073	20.76
Residential-Med/Low Density --> URML	3429.6904	8474.9365	2.79
Forest-Deciduous --> FRSD	5620.0713	13887.4773	4.58
Oats --> OATS	1154.7145	2853.3572	0.94
spring wheat --> SWHT	939.9262	2322.6045	0.77
Industrial --> UIDU	486.4242	1201.9784	0.40
water --> WATR	399.5843	987.3929	0.33
Garden or Canning Peas --> PEAS	164.9046	407.4875	0.13

SOILS:	Area [ha]	Area[acres]	%wat.Area
ABe	20881.1193	51598.2898	17.01
ARh	18161.2783	44877.4267	14.79
FLe	3764.3048	9301.7853	3.07
GLe	11470.0352	28343.0305	9.34
GLm	3414.1375	8436.5044	2.78
HSS	5522.0747	13645.3226	4.50
LVg	27575.6240	68140.7457	22.46
LVh	3939.9360	9735.7789	3.21
PLe	724.5577	1790.4182	0.59
ABd	13263.1204	32773.8337	10.80
ABg	10693.5187	26424.2194	8.71
RGe	1296.5521	3203.8451	1.06
ARG	510.8985	1262.4558	0.42
PZh	904.2102	2234.3485	0.74
HSF	528.5801	1306.1478	0.43

Fig. 15. HRU definition summary report.

Fig.16. Starting definition of weather data.

Fig. 17. Weather station definition form.

6. Adding weather data requires

- a. Invoking a weather station definition dialogue (Fig. 16).
- b. Selecting “Custom Database” and specifying its file name for the lists of stations (weather generator **meteostc.dbf**, rainfall **pcplist.dbf**, temperature **tmpelist.dbf**, relative humidity **hmdlist.dbf**, solar radiation **sollist.dbf**, and wind speed **wndlist.dbf**) for all meteorological data types, see Fig. 17.
- c. The meteorological data will be further (during writing SWAT setups, p.7) assigned to every of the subbasins of Lithuania from the meteorological data files (**wgnXX.dbf**, **pcpXX.dbf**, **tmpXX**, **hmdXX.dbf**, **slrXX.dbf**, **wndXX.dbf**) of closest of the meteorological stations (See Fig. 2).

Fig. 18. Writing prepared data to geodatabase.

7. Writing data tables to geodatabase is performed via selection from the pull-down menu, see Fig. 18. This step finalises the creation of a raw SWAT setup for particular watershed. During the raw setup generation ARCSWAT requests multiple selections. The recommended answers are shown in Fig. 19.

Steps 1 to 7 were performed for all watersheds creating the raw SWAT setups in separate directories.

Fig.19. The pop-up selections during the writing of SWAT tables of the raw setup.

3.3. Preparation of data and creation of initial setups

Let us consider the preparation of data and their further filling into geodatabase after creation of raw SWAT setups. We refer to the data files and Python scripts for their transfer into initial SWAT setups throughout this Section. The location of data files and full nomenclature of the scripts is presented in Chapter 4.

1. Data for **atmospheric deposition of nitrogen**. Atmospheric deposition data were acquired from "EMEP/MS-C-W modelled air concentrations and depositions", see web reference at http://webdab.emep.int/Unified_Model_Results/. The gridded data of wet, dry and total deposition of reduced (NH_x) and oxidised (NO_x) nitrogen (in mg/m²/year) are provided there for each year. The grid of precipitation (mm/year) for each year are also provided. Year 2005 was selected as the base for the computation of atmospheric deposition. Atmospheric deposition of nitrogen was introduced in the model setup as the parameter „Concentration of nitrogen in rainfall" (**basins.bsn** file, variable RCN). The gridded EMEP data was geometrically intersected with the watershed, and the total amount of deposited NH_x and NO_x (totN) and precipitation (P) was calculated.
 - a. The respective prepared data files are **atm_depos_poly_y2005_totNOx.shp**, **atm_depos_poly_y2005_totNHx.shp** and **atm_depos_poly_y2005_prec.shp**.
 - b. The script **atmosphericDeposition.py** contains a procedure writing the atmospheric deposition to **ArcSWAT.mdb** file as a concentration of nitrogen in rainfall, by intersecting deposition shape files with given setup.
2. The pollution **point source** database (location, table of loads) was transformed into shape file **Point_source.shp**. The table of loads contains annual discharge of water, annual loads of suspended sediments, BOD₇, nitrogen (N_{tot}, possible N-NO₃, N-NH₄, N-NO₂), phosphorus (P_{tot}, possible P-PO₄). The point source data was pre-processed as follows:
 - a. The annual load of SS, BOD₇, N-NO₃, N-NH₄, N-NO₂, N_{org}, P-PO₄, P_{org} was calculated for each point source using the following approach:
 - i. Load is 0 for particular year if there is no record in the database.
 - ii. If P-PO₄ data is missing then $P\text{-PO}_4 = P_{\text{org}} = P_{\text{tot}}/2$, otherwise $P_{\text{org}} = P_{\text{tot}} - P\text{-PO}_4$.
 - iii. If inorganic nitrogen components data is missing then $N\text{-NO}_3 = N_{\text{org}} = N_{\text{tot}}/2$, otherwise $N_{\text{org}} = N_{\text{tot}} - N_{\text{inorg}}$.
 - b. The point source data is summarised in a file **point_source.shp**.
 - c. Point sources were summed-up for each of particular subbasins and added to ArcSWAT setups at the upstream points of the respective reaches by Python script **.updatePointSources.py**.
3. The **[agricultural] management praxis** for the whole territory of Lithuania was applied to calculate the **loads from the diffuse sources** under the following

assumptions which differ for the five land use classes (see Table 9):

Table 10. Crop identifier and particular plant parameters for different land use types.

Land use code	CROPID	Land use class	PHU	PLANTHU	HarvestHU	FERTHU
AGRC	3	Agricultural	1507	0.03	1.1	0.2
AGRR	2	Agricultural	966	0.21	1.2	0.21
ALFA	52	Agricultural	1057	0.12	1	0.2
APPL	93	Forest				
BARL	31	Agricultural	1422	0.12	1.1	0.2
BROM	37	Pasture				
CANP	75	Agricultural	1328	0.12	1.1	0.2
CLVR	54	Pasture				
CORN	19	Agricultural	966	0.21	1.2	0.21
CRRT	72	Agricultural	1086	0.15	1.1	0.2
EGGP	86	Agricultural	634	0.3	1	0.3
FESC	38	Agricultural	1106	0.12	1	0.2
FLAX	65	Agricultural	1228	0.12	1.2	0.12
FPEA	62	Agricultural	1178	0.12	1.2	0.2
FRSD	7	Forest				
FRSE	8	Forest				
FRST	6	Forest				
GRBN	84	Agricultural	596	0.3	1.2	0.3
LENT	60	Agricultural	1041	0.12	1.2	0.2
OATS	32	Agricultural	1331	0.12	1.1	0.2
ORCD	4	Agricultural	1086	0.15	1	0.2
PEAS	63	Agricultural	870	0.12	1.2	0.2
POTA	70	Agricultural	938	0.15	1.1	0.2
RYE	30	Agricultural	1014	0.12	1.1	0.2
RYEG	44	Pasture				
SCRN	21	Agricultural	348	0.42	1.2	0.42
SGBT	69	Agricultural	1185	0.12	1.1	0.2
SOYB	56	Agricultural	653	0.3	1.2	0.3
STRW	91	Agricultural	609	0.3	1	0.3
SWHT	27	Agricultural	1507	0.12	1.1	0.2
TIMO	35	Agricultural	803	0.21	1	0.21
TOMA	92	Agricultural	634	0.3	1	0.3
UIDU, URHD		Urban				
URLD, URLM		Urban				
WATR, WETH	18,14	Water				
WETF	10	Forest				
WPAS	14	Pasture				
WWHT	28	Agricultural	1507	0.03	1.1	0.2

- a. The standard ArcSWAT parameters were assumed for calculating loads from **urban** territories (land use type *Urban*).
- b. No operations (planting, fertilising, harvesting) were assumed for the **forests**. Initial biomass *initbio=100000 kg/ha* and number of heat units to bring plants to maturity *PHU=3000* (i.e. avoiding the bringing trees to maturity within vegetation season) were assumed. The plant selection for the forest areas were apple trees for gardens (APPL), pine-trees for evergreen forests (FRSE), oaks for deciduous forests (FRSD).
- c. For the **agricultural** land the management praxis contained 6 steps for each agricultural land use – spring plow, planting, fertilizer application, continuous fertilisation, kill and harvest operation, and fall plow. The praxis was applied as follows:
 - i. General **spring plow** operation (*tillID=2* from *till.dat*), was scheduled at fraction of base zero heat units equal to 0.02. Sping plow was not implemented for landuse codes AGRC and WWHT (*cropid* 3 and 28)
 - ii. **Planting** operation was scheduled at a fraction of base zero heat units dependent on the crop (see Table 10, column *PLANTHU*). The numbers of potential heat units to bring plants to maturity are also included in Table 10, column *PHU*. *PLANTHU* and *PHU* were calculated by Potential Heat Unit Program <http://swatmodel.tamu.edu/software/potential-heat-unit-program/>. Required input data items for this program are (1) the weather long-term maximum and minimum temperature data, (2) the base or minimum temperature required for the plant growth, (3) the average number of days for the plant to reach maturity. The long term temperature data was taken from the Dotnuva meteorological station. Base temperatures and number of days to reach maturity for the considered plants (i.e. input to the PHU program) are summarized in Table 11.
 - iii. **Fertilizer application**. Fertilizers were applied as two separate applications – one for mineral nitrogen and another for phosphorus, scheduled at fraction of plant heat units *FERTHU*, see Table 10. The scheduling of fertilizer application was selected as $FERTHU = \max(0, 2; PLANTHU)$. The amount of applied nitrogen and phosphorus was calculated from the fertilizer database (fert id 1 and 2 , respectively). The geometric shapes of HRUs within each setup (layer *FullHRU*) were geometrically intersected with the administrative division of supplied agricultural statistics data (layer ***counties2004.shp***, data by counties) obtaining layer ***FullHRU_counties2004*** in the ArcMap project of each of the setups. The fields MINN_HA and MINP_HA, representing mineral nitrogen and mineral phosphorus application per hectare of agricultural land were used to calculate the corresponding amount of applied fertilizer (FRT_KG) in each of the HRUs. It should be noted that one HRU can be located in multiple counties, therefore area weighted average for each of the counties that are present in the particular HRU was calculated.
 - iv. **Continuous fertilization** represents application of manure. The field *SGV_TANKIS* from the agricultural statistics data (layer ***counties2004.shp***, data by counties), representing density of

standard animals per hectare of agricultural land was used, assuming that each of the standard animals is annually producing 100 kg of nitrogen and 17 kg of phosphorus. Special fertilizer type (*fertID=55*, *fertname=SGV*) was introduced for this application to specify the amounts of organic and inorganic fertilizers. Each unit of this fertilizer contains (1) 0.25 units of mineral nitrogen, 99% of which is ammonia; (2) 0.07 units of mineral phosphorus; (3) 0.75 units of organic nitrogen; (4) 0.1 unit of organic phosphorus. The same geospatial intersection layer as in p.(iii) was used. The continuous fertilization was scheduled to start at a fraction of potential plant heat units 0.15 and last for *FERT_DAYS=190* days. Application frequency (*IFRT_FREQ*) was set to 1 day. Thus, the amount of fertilizer applied in each application is $CFRT_KG=SGV_TANKIS*100/FERT_DAYS$

Table 11. List of considered plants and their parameters.

Abbreviation	Full name	Optimal temperature	Base temperature	Drying HU	Days to reach maturity
AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown	18	0	0.1	110
AGRR	Agricultural Land-Row Crops	25	8	0.2	120
ALFA	Alfalfa	20	4	0	90
BARL	Spring Barley	25	0	0.1	105
CANP	Spring Canola-Polish	21	5	0.1	120
CORN	Corn	25	8	0.2	120
CRRT	Carrot	24	7	0.1	120
EGGP	Eggplant	26	15	0	100
FESC	Tall Fescue	15	0	0	90
FLAX	Flax	22.5	5	0.2	110
FPEA	Field Peas	15	1	0.2	100
GRBN	Green Beans	19	10	0.2	85
LENT	Lentils	20	3	0.2	85
OATS	Oats	15	0	0.1	105
ORCD	Orchard	20	7	0	120
PEAS	Garden or Canning Peas	14	5	0.2	100
POTA	Potato	22	7	0.1	100
RYE	Rye	12.5	0	0.1	90
SCRN	Sweet Corn	24	12	0.2	120
SGBT	Sugarbeet	18	4	0.1	100
SOYB	Soybean	25	10	0.2	120
STRW	Strawberry	32	10	0	90
SWHT	Spring Wheat	18	0	0.1	110
TIMO	Timothy	25	8	0	90
TOMA	Tomato	22	10	0	100
WWHT	Winter Wheat	18	0	0.1	110

- v. **Harvest and kill** operation was scheduled at a fraction of plant heat units between 1.0 and 1.2 (see Table 10). Depending on a crop type it accounts for the necessary additional crop drying time (see table 11).

- vi. General **fall plow** operation ($tillID=1$ from *till.dat*) was scheduled at fraction of base zero heat units equal to 0.9. It should be noted here that original source code of SWAT2009 was modified to allow for only base zero scheduling of tillage operations. This is necessary to schedule the autumn plow operation after the plants are harvested.
 - d. For the **pastures** the continuous fertilization and grazing was applied. The permanent (without planting and harvesting) grass cover of pastures was assumed with initial biomass 5000 kg/ha and the number of heat units to bring plant to maturity 3000 (i.e. to avoid bringing grass to maturity during one vegetation season). The continuous fertilizing was applied identically to continuous fertilization of the agricultural land (p.8-c-iv). The grazing of the grass by standard animals was assumed simultaneously with continuous fertilisation for 190 days long period starting at $f=0,15$.
 - e. The Python script **updateManagement.py** applies the agricultural management operations to ArcSWAT geodatabase file, including mineral fertilizer application, organic fertilizer application by animals and animal grazing. It uses the data from the agricultural statistics file **counties_2004.shp**.
4. The **drainage** data for the setups was prepared from the supplied melioration database.
 - a. First, the shape files from the melioration database was joined in one shape file.
 - b. Second, the geometric shapes of HRUs within each setup (layer *FullHRU*) were geometrically intersected with the melioration data obtaining layer *FullHRU_melioration* in the ArcMap project of each of the setups.
 - c. Third, the relative area R_{melior} of the meliorated territory was calculated for each HRU dividing the sum of areas with "TIPAS=D" by the total area of respective HRU. We assumed that $TDRAIN_r=0$ if $R_{melior}<5\%$.
 - d. We set SWAT parameter $TDRAIN=TDRAIN0/R_{melior}$, here $TDRAIN0$ is the calibration parameter. Note, that the drainage data is included in the setups but is not activated in the calculations and calibrated due to the present version of SWAT2009 does not transfer the water quality parameters through the drainage.
 - e. The Python script **UpdateDrainage.py** creates tile drainage information in SWAT geodatabase by intersecting drainage data from **all.shp** with a particular setup.
5. The **wetland** parameters in PND file are prepared as follows.
 - a. The wetland fraction for each subbasin WET_FR is calculated as the sum of areas of the land use type $WETF$ and $WETN$ ($AREA_WTL$) divided by the subbasin area.
 - b. The wetland areas at normal and maximum water level WET_NSA and WET_MXSA are assumed equal to $AREA_WTL$.
 - c. For the calculation of the wetland volumes WET_NVOL and WET_MXVOL

these areas were multiplied by 2 m and 3 m, respectively.

- d. The above operations with the SWAT geodatabase are performed by Python script **updateWetlands.py**.
6. The **lake and pond** information from the shape file **Lakes_and_ponds_for_modelling.shp** is processed by the Python script **updateLakes.py**. It intersects the lakes and ponds with setups and updates MDB setup parameters. After that the scripts disables taking into account the lakes, because there is an error in SWAT software related to double accounting of lake area in precipitation.
 7. The GIS layer of **reservoirs** is used from shape file **reservoirs_with_parameters.shp** for reservoir parameters.
 - a. Only the reservoirs that are located on the river network (determined by the spatial join of layer *reservoirs_with_parameters* and layer *Reach* of each of the setups) are used.
 - b. The spatial intersection of this layer and subbasin geometric shape (layer *Watershed*) was performed to determine the actual subbasin to which the reservoir is attached (and divide the reservoir if it belongs to more than one subbasin) obtaining layer *reservoirs* for each of the setups.
 - c. The reservoir parameters representing area at the emergency spillway level, volume at the emergency spillway level, the area at the principal spillway level, and volume at the principal spillway level (*RES_ESA*, *RES_EVOL*, *RES_PSA*, *RES_PVOL*) were obtained as $RES_ESA = sav11$, $RES_EVOL = vav11/10$, $RES_PSA = snp11$, $RES_PVOL = vnpl1/10$. The initial volume of water in the reservoir (*RES_VOL*) was set equal to *RES_PVOL*.
 - d. The reservoirs were assumed to operate as „uncontrolled reservoir with the annual release rate” (*IRESKO=0*). Corresponding annual release rate (*RES_RR*) was assumed to be the principal volume of the reservoir divided by 1 year, i.e. $RES_RR = RES_PVOL * 1000 / (365 * 86400)$ [m³/s].
 - e. The Python script **updateReservoirs.py** intersects and creates reservoirs for setups, and fills the parameters needed for reservoirs in the SWAT geodatabase.
 - f. The Python script **updatePndResAreas.py** should be executed after filling the lake, pond and reservoir parameters in the SWAT setups. This procedure subtracts the lake and pond, and reservoir areas from the subbasin area to avoid its double accounting by SWAT.
 8. The **meteorological data** is further processed in the transition before the raw and initial SWAT setups.
 - a. The files **weatherdata.sta** (containing co-ordinates of weather stations and **weatherdata.txt** (containing observations at these stations) were created for further use of script **MDB2SWAT.py** (see p.10c below). Note that these two files replace all the file system employed by ArcSWAT (station lists **meteostc.dbf**, **pcplist.dbf**, **tmplist.dbf**, **hmdlist.dbf**, **sollist.dbf**, **wndlist.dbf** and corresponding multiple data files **wgnXX.dbf**, **pcpXX.dbf**, **tmpXX**, **hmdXX.dbf**, **slrXX.dbf**, **wndXX.dbf**). Once the raw setups are

created (Section 3.2) the user may keep all hydrometeorological input data in files **weatherdata.sta** and **weatherdata.txt**.

- b. The comparison of the distribution of the annual precipitation in the file **SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\Climatestations\stations.shp** supplied by EPA (the station location is shown in Fig. 2 as precipitation stations) indicated that the data series of precipitation in the meteorological station do not represent the spatial distribution of the precipitation with sufficient resolution. Therefore the annual precipitation p_{pst} was assigned to each of the subbasins by means of kriging interpolation of the precipitation station data (see subbasin-related annual precipitation in Fig. 2). The precipitation correction factors $rfnc1...rfnc12$ were calculated as p_{pst}/p_{mst} , here p_{mst} is a annual precipitation for particular subbasin, calculated from the data series of meteorological station.
- c. The Python procedure of implementing precipitation correction in ArcSWAT geodatabase is **precipitationCorrection.py**. It uses shape files **BasinGCS.shp**, **stations_vs_real.shp** and database **statpcp.dbf**.

Fig.20. Sequence (scheme) of running Python scripts for creation of initial setups from the raw setups.

9. The **transboundary data** for the catchments which partially extend outside the territory of Lithuania are prepared:
 - a. The catchment areas of watersheds outside the territory of Lithuania are summarized in the shape file **transboundary.shp**. Python script **transboundary.py** adds this area to the catchment area of particular catchment modifying the geodatabase.
 - b. The transboundary inflow through Nemunas and Neris (time series of Q and water quality data) are prepared in files **QObs.txt**, **Qobs.sta**, **WQObs.txt** and **WQObs.sta**. These files include, respectively, station location ("sta" files) and

observed time series ('txt' files) for discharge (Q) and water quality parameters (WQ). Python script **transBoundaryInlets.py** adds these time series to SWAT setups.

10. The initial SWAT setups for all watersheds are created from the raw ArcSWAT geodatabases automatically by the system of scripts after preparation of the data of pp. 1-9. The scheme of procedure is illustrated in Fig. 20.

- a. The Python script **Main.py** is invoked (either from command line or by batch file **run.bat**). This script reads the predefined (i.e. user defined) configuration of the water quality modeling system from file **Settings.py** and iterates through all setups performing the actions (b-d) below.
- b. Running script **updateAll.py** which updates the contents of ArcSWAT geodatabase by means of
 - i. Invoking the previously described procedures (p.1-9a above).
 - ii. Setting the calculation time period and the frequency of writing the results during calculations by Python procedure **defineSimulationPeriod.py**.
 - iii. Adding dummy upstream inlets to all the setups which are not the upstream setups by Python script **updateInlets.py**. The list of these setups is contained in the file **baseini_konekcijas.txt**.
 - iv. Replacing SWAT model coefficients by the Python script **updateCoefficients.py**. The coefficient values are taken from the file **coefficients.txt**.
- c. Invoking script **MDB2SWAT.py** which creates SWAT setup files from the ArcSWAT geodatabase, i.e. ArcSWAT setup. The meteorological data are assigned to every of the subbasins of Lithuania from the closest of the meteorological station (See Fig. 2) filling the weather data into SWAT setups from the ASCII files **weatherdata.sta** and **weatherdata.txt**.
- d. Invoking script **transboundaryInlets.py** which adds the inflowing time series for the Nemunas and Neris setups.

4 Modeling system and performing calculations

4.1. Modeling system

Both the ArcSWAT and SWAT model setups are prepared for all watersheds of Lithuania and supplied with necessary input data for the time period 2000-2010 in PAIC & ELLE (2012a) and updated in PAIC & ELLE (2012c). All setups of the modelling system are summarised in Table 12.

Table 12. The list of watershed setups for the territory of Lithuania. Marking of lines in the table separates river basins (regions).

Basin (region)	SWAT Watershed	Setup (Directory)
Bartuva	Apšė	Bartuva/Apse
Bartuva	Bartuva	Bartuva/Bartuva_Skuodas
Dauguva	497	Dauguva/497
Dauguva	514	Dauguva/514
Dauguva	Birvėta	Dauguva/Bivyte
Dauguva	Drūkša	Dauguva/Druksa
Dauguva	Dysna	Dauguva/Dysna
Dauguva	Lukšta	Dauguva/Ilukste
Dauguva	Laukesa	Dauguva/Laukesa
Dauguva	Rauda	Dauguva/Rauda
Dauguva	Raukuta	Dauguva/Raukuta
Dubysa	Dubysa	Dubysa/Dubysa
Jūra	Ežeruona	Jura/Ezeruona
Jūra	Jūra	Jura/Jura_Gals
Jūra	Jūra	Jura/Jura_Taurage
Jūra	Šešuvis	Jura/Sesupe_Skirgalai
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	194	Lielupe_MI/194
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	198	Lielupe_MI/198
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	213	Lielupe_MI/213
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	220	Lielupe_MI/220
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Alėja	Lielupe_MI/Aleja
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Audruvė	Lielupe_MI/Audruve
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Beržtalys	Lielupe_MI/Berstalis
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Kivė	Lielupe_MI/Kive
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Leparė	Lielupe_MI/Lepare
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Oglainė	Lielupe_MI/Oglaine
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Platonė	Lielupe_MI/Platone
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Plonyte	Lielupe_MI/Plonyte
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Šešėvė	Lielupe_MI/Seseve
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Sidabra	Lielupe_MI/Sidarba
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Švėtė	Lielupe_MI/Svete
Lielupes mažiieji intakai	Švėtelė	Lielupe_MI/Svetele

Lielupes mašieji intakai	Svirkalnis	Lielupe_MI/Svirkalnis
Lielupes mašieji intakai	Švitinys	Lielupe_MI/Svitinys
Lielupes mašieji intakai	Vilkija	Lielupe_MI/Vilikija1
Lielupes mašieji intakai	Virčiuvis	Lielupe_MI/Virciuvis
Lielupes mašieji intakai	Viršytis	Lielupe_MI/Virsytis
Lielupes mašieji intakai	Yslykis	Lielupe_MI/Ylksys
Merkys	Merkys	Merkys/Merkys
Merkys	Ūla – Pelesa	Merkys/Pelesa
Merkys	Šalčia	Merkys/Salčia
Merkys	Varėnė	Merkys/Varene
Merkys	Verseka	Merkys/Verseka
Minija	Minija	Minija/Minija_Kartena
Minija	Minija	Minija/Minija_zem_kartenas
Minija	Veiviržas	Minija/Veivirzas
Minija	Žvelsa	Minija/Zvelsa
Mūša	Daugyvenė	Musa/Daugyvene
Mūša	Kruoja	Musa/Kruoja
Mūša	Kulpė	Musa/Kulpe
Mūša	Lėvuos	Musa/Levuo
Mūša	Mažupė	Musa/Mazupe
Mūša	Mūša	Musa/Musa_kopa
Mūša	Pyvesa	Musa/Pyvesa
Mūša	Šiladis	Musa/Siladys
Mūša	Tatula	Musa/Tatula
Nemunas	Baltoji Ančia	Nemunas/Baltoji
Nemunas	Gėgė	Nemunas/Gege
Nemunas	Jiesia	Nemunas/Jiesiai
Nemunas	Miltuva	Nemunas/Miltuva
Nemunas	Nemunas	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nemunas	Peršėkė	Nemunas/Perseke
Nemunas	Strėva	Nemunas/Streva
Nemunas	Strėva	Nemunas/Streva_ecl_semeliskes
Nemunas	Šyša	Nemunas/Sysa_Silute
Nemunas	Verknė	Nemunas/Verkne_Vebyksles
Nemunėlis	Apaščia	Nemunelis/Apasciai
Nemunėlis	Nemunėlis	Nemunelis/Nemunelis_LT
Neris	Musė	Neris/Muse
Neris	Neris	Neris/Neris_upe
Neris	Vilnia	Neris/Vilnia
Neris	Vokė	Neris/Voke
Nevėžis	Aluona	Nevezis/Aluona
Nevėžis	Barupė	Nevezis/Barupe
Nevėžis	Kiršinas	Nevezis/Kirstina
Nevėžis	Nevėžis	Nevezis/Nevezis
Nevėžis	Obelis	Nevezis/Obelis

Nevėžis	Nevėžis	Nevezis/Panevezis
Nevėžis	Smilga	Nevezis/Smilga
Nevėžis	Šušvė	Nevezis/Susve
Nevėžis	Upytė	Nevezis/Upyte
Pajūrio upės	1127	Parejais/1127
Pajūrio upės	1129	Parejais/1129
Pajūrio upės	1131	Parejais/1131
Pajūrio upės	1158	Parejais/1158
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kretinga
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_Kapa
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_laguna1
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_laguna2
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_laguna3
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_laguna4
Pajūrio upės	No name	Parejais/Kursu_laguna5
Pajūrio upės	Ošupis	Parejais/Osupis2
Pajūrio upės	Akmėna	Parejais/Pareja_Akmėne
Pajūrio upės	Smėltalė	Parejais/Smėltale
Prieglius	Prieglius	Prieglius/Prieglius
Šėšupė	Jotija	Sesupe/Jotijaa
Šėšupė	Nova	Sesupe/Nova
Šėšupė	Pilvė	Sesupe/Pilve
Šėšupė	Šėšupė	Sesupe/Sesupe
Šėšupė	Šėšupė	Sesupe/Sesupe_upst
Šėšupė	Širvinta	Sesupe/Sirvinta
Šėšupė	Višakis	Sesupe/Viskakis1
Šventoji	Jara	Shventoji/Jara
Šventoji	Šventoji	Shventoji/Shventoji_A
Šventoji	Šventoji	Shventoji/Shventoji_K
Šventoji	Siesartis	Shventoji/Siesartis
Šventoji	Širvinta	Shventoji/Sirvinta
Šventoji	Suraiža-Virinta	Shventoji/Suraiza
Šventoji	Vyžuona	Shventoji/Vyžuona
Šventoji	Šventoji	Sveventoji/Sventoji
Šventoji	Šventoji	Sveventoji/Sventoji_Klaip
Venta	222	Venta/222
Venta	223	Venta/223
Venta	Dabikinė	Venta/Dabikina
Venta	Uogys	Venta/Uogys
Venta	Vadakstis	Venta/Vadakstis
Venta	Varduva	Venta/Varduva
Venta	Venta	Venta/Venta
Venta	Virvyčia	Venta/Virvyčia
Žeimėna	Dumbėlė-Kiauna	Zeimėna/Dumble1
Žeimėna	Žeimėna	Zeimėna/Kaltena

Žeimena	Lakaja	Zeimena/Lakaja
Žeimena	Stirnelė	Zeimena/Stirnele
Žeimena	Žeimena	Zeimena/Zeimena

The setups are grouped (regionalized) into 19 groups (color separated in Tables 12-13). Both the SWAT and ArcSWAT setups are provided for each watershed from Table 12 in the separate subdirectory (the 3rd column of Table 12); the respective directory names correspond to the group (or region).

The SWAT model parameter values in all watersheds are set according to the regionalised calibration results (see Section 4.5) and provided both in all the setups and the file **coefficients.txt**.

Figure 21. Map of watersheds color-coded by their hierarchical level.

Any particular watershed in Table 12 could either (1) be the upstream watershed or (2) receive the inflow from the other model watershed or (3) receive the inflow from transboundary inlets. All watersheds are classified to levels 1, 2, 3 and 4 according to their position in the river network (see Fig. 21):

- Level 1 watersheds are upstream watersheds that do not receive inflows from any other watershed.
- Level 2 watersheds receive inflows from at least one level 1 watershed.
- Level 3 watersheds receive inflows from at least one level 2 watershed.
- Level 4 watersheds receive inflows from at least one level 3 watershed.

Map of color-coded hierarchical levels of watersheds is shown in Figure 21. The hierarchical levels of the watersheds are summarized in Table 13. Information whether a particular watershed receives transboundary waters and the type of the watershed outflow (neighbouring country or receiving watershed) is also included in this table.

Table 13. List of watershed levels in a hierarchical structure of setups. Marking of lines in the table separates river basins (regions).

Directory (setup name)	Transboundary inlet	Level	Outflow (transboundary or setup name)
Bartuva/Apse	YES	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Bartuva/Bartuva_Skuodas	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Dauguva/497	NO	1	<i>Belorus</i>
Dauguva/514	NO	1	<i>Belorus</i>
Dauguva/Bivyte	YES	1	<i>Belorus</i>
Dauguva/Drukisa	NO	1	<i>Belorus</i>
Dauguva/Dysna	NO	1	<i>Belorus</i>
Dauguva/Ilukste	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Dauguva/Laukesa	NO	1	<i>Belorus</i>
Dauguva/Rauda	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Dauguva/Raukuta	NO	1	<i>Belorus</i>
Dubysa/Dubysa	NO	1	Nemunas/Nemunas
Jura/Ezeruona	NO	1	Jura/Jura_gals
Jura/Jura_Gals	NO	2	Nemunas/Nemunas
Jura/Jura_Taurage	NO	1	Jura/Jura_gals
Jura/Sesupe_Skirgalai	NO	1	Jura/Jura_gals
Lielupe_MI/194	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/198	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/213	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/220	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Aleja	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Audruve	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Berstalis	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Kive	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Lepare	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Oglaine	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Platone	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Plonyte	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Seseve	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Sidarba	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Svete	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Svetele	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Svirkalnis	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Svitinys	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Vilikija1	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>
Lielupe_MI/Virciuvis	NO	1	<i>Latvia</i>

Lielupe_MI/Virsytis	NO	1	Latvia
Lielupe_MI/Ylksys	NO	1	Latvia
Merkys/Merkys	YES	2	Nemunas/Nemunas
Merkys/Pelesa	NO	1	Merkys/Merkys
Merkys/Salcia	YES	1	Merkys/Merkys
Merkys/Varene	NO	1	Merkys/Merkys
Merkys/Verseka	YES	1	Merkys/Merkys
Minija/Minija_Kartena	NO	1	Minija/Minija_zem_kartenas
Minija/Minija_zem_kartenas	NO	2	Nemunas/Nemunas
Minija/Veivirzas	NO	1	Minija/Minija_zem_kartenas
Minija/Zvelsa	NO	1	Minija/Minija_zem_kartenas
Musa/Daugyvene	NO	1	Musa/Musa_kopa
Musa/Kruoja	NO	1	Musa/Musa_kopa
Musa/Kulpe	NO	1	Musa/Musa_kopa
Musa/Levuo	NO	1	Musa/Musa_kopa
Musa/Mazupe	NO	1	Musa/Musa_kopa
Musa/Musa_kopa	YES	2	Latvia
Musa/Pyvesa	NO	1	Musa/Musa_kopa
Musa/Siladys	NO	1	Musa/Musa_kopa
Musa/Tatula	NO	1	Musa/Musa_kopa
Nemunas/Baltoji	NO	1	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nemunas/Gege	NO	1	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nemunas/Jiesiai	NO	1	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nemunas/Miltuva	NO	1	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nemunas/Nemunas	YES, Q/WQ series	4	Baltic Sea
Nemunas/Perseke	NO	1	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nemunas/Streva	NO	1	Nemunas/Streva_ecl_semeliskes
Nemunas/Streva_ecl_semeliskes	NO	2	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nemunas/Sysa_Silute	NO	1	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nemunas/Verkne_Vebyksles	NO	1	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nemunelis/Apasciai	NO	1	Nemunelis/Nemunelis_LT
Nemunelis/Nemunelis_LT	YES	2	Latvia
Neris/Muse	NO	1	Neris/Neris_upe
Neris/Neris_upe	YES, Q/WQ series	3	Nemunas/Nemunas
Neris/Vilnia	NO	1	Neris/Neris_upe
Neris/Voke	NO	1	Neris/Neris_upe
Nevezis/Aluona	NO	1	Nevezis/Nevezis
Nevezis/Barupe	NO	1	Nevezis/Nevezis
Nevezis/Kirstina	NO	1	Nevezis/Nevezis
Nevezis/Nevezis	NO	2	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nevezis/Obelis	NO	1	Nevezis/Nevezis
Nevezis/Panevezis	NO	1	Nevezis/Nevezis
Nevezis/Smilga	NO	1	Nevezis/Nevezis
Nevezis/Susve	NO	1	Nevezis/Nevezis
Nevezis/Upyte	NO	1	Nevezis/Nevezis

Parejais/1127	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Parejais/1129	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Parejais/1131	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Parejais/1158	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Parejais/Kretinga	NO	1	Parejais/Pareja_Akmene
Parejais/Kursu_Kapa	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Parejais/Kursu_laguna1	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Parejais/Kursu_laguna2	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Parejais/Kursu_laguna3	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Parejais/Kursu_laguna4	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Parejais/Kursu_laguna5	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Parejais/Osupis2	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Parejais/Pareja_Akmene	NO	2	Baltic Sea
Parejais/Smeltale	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Prieglius/Prieglius	NO	1	Russia
Sesupe/Jotijaa	NO	1	Russia
Sesupe/Nova	NO	1	Sesupe/Sesupe
Sesupe/Pilve	NO	1	Sesupe/Sesupe
Sesupe/Sesupe	YES	2	Russia
Sesupe/Sesupe_upst	NO	1	Sesupe/Sesupe
Sesupe/Sirvinta	NO	1	Sesupe/Sesupe
Sesupe/Viskakis1	NO	1	Sesupe/Sesupe
Shventoji/Jara	NO	1	Shventoji/Shventoji_K
Shventoji/Shventoji_A	NO	1	Shventoji/Shventoji_K
Shventoji/Shventoji_K	NO	2	Neris/Neris_upe
Shventoji/Sierastis	NO	1	Shventoji/Shventoji_K
Shventoji/Sirvinta	NO	1	Shventoji/Shventoji_K
Shventoji/Suraiza	NO	1	Shventoji/Shventoji_K
Shventoji/Vyzuona	NO	1	Shventoji/Shventoji_K
Sveentoji/Sventoji	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Sveentoji/Sventoji_Klaip	NO	1	Baltic Sea
Venta/222	YES	1	Latvia
Venta/223	NO	1	Latvia
Venta/Dabikina	NO	1	Venta/Venta
Venta/Uogys	NO	1	Venta/Venta
Venta/Vadakstis	YES	1	Latvia
Venta/Varduva	NO	1	Latvia
Venta/Venta	NO	2	Latvia
Venta/Virvycia	NO	1	Venta/Venta
Zeimena/Dumble1	NO	1	Zeimena/Zeimena
Zeimena/Kaltena	NO	1	Zeimena/Zeimena
Zeimena/Lakaja	NO	1	Zeimena/Zeimena
Zeimena/Stirnele	NO	1	Zeimena/Zeimena
Zeimena/Zeimena	NO	2	Neris/Neris_upe

Several watersheds have the part of territories outside Lithuania. These transboundary watersheds are treated in two different ways:

1. The times series of discharge and water quality parameters are specified for Nemunas and Neris. The respective data series are prepared in files **QObs.txt**, **QObs.sta**, **WQObs.txt** and **WQObs.sta**. These files include, respectively, station location (“sta” files) and observed time series (‘txt’ files) for discharge (Q) and water quality parameters (WQ). Python script **transBoundaryInlets.py** adds these time series to SWAT setups.
2. The area of the other transboundary watersheds is increased by adding the area outside Lithuania to the respective setups. The catchment areas of watersheds outside the territory of Lithuania are summarized in the shape file **transboundary.shp**. Python script **transboundary.py** adds this area to the catchment area of particular catchment modifying the geodatabase.

The hierarchical structure of the modeling system requires establishment of connections between watersheds. The coupling of inflows/outflows is summarised in Table 13 and included in the modeling system as file **Baseini_konekcijas.txt**.

Table 14. List of connections between watersheds.

Inlet		Outlet
Directory	Inlet file	Directory
Jura/Jura_gals	1i.dat	Jura/Jura_Taurage
Jura/Jura_gals	1i.dat	Jura/Sesupe_Skirgalai
Jura/Jura_gals	2i.dat	Jura/Ezeruona
Merkys/Merkys	11i.dat	Merkys/Verseka
Merkys/Merkys	14i.dat	Merkys/Varene
Merkys/Merkys	16i.dat	Merkys/Pelesa
Merkys/Merkys	9i.dat	Merkys/Salcia
Minija/Minija_zem_kartenas	1i.dat	Minija/Minija_Kartena
Minija/Minija_zem_kartenas	2i.dat	Minija/Zvelsa
Minija/Minija_zem_kartenas	5i.dat	Minija/Veivirzas
Musa/Musa_kopa	11i.dat	Musa/Mazupe
Musa/Musa_kopa	13i.dat	Musa/Kruoja
Musa/Musa_kopa	2i.dat	Musa/Tatula
Musa/Musa_kopa	5i.dat	Musa/Levuo
Musa/Musa_kopa	5i.dat	Musa/Pyvesa
Musa/Musa_kopa	7i.dat	Musa/Siladys
Musa/Musa_kopa	8i.dat	Musa/Kulpe
Musa/Musa_kopa	9i.dat	Musa/Daugyvene
Nemunas/Nemunas	10i.dat	Nemunas/Miltuva
Nemunas/Nemunas	11i.dat	Dubysa/Dubysa
Nemunas/Nemunas	14i.dat	Nevezis/Nevezis
Nemunas/Nemunas	15i.dat	Nemunas/Jiesiai
Nemunas/Nemunas	17i.dat	Neris/Neris_upe
Nemunas/Nemunas	18i.dat	Nemunas/Streva_ecl_semeliskes
Nemunas/Nemunas	1i.dat	Minija/Minija_zem_kartenas

Nemunas/Nemunas	21i.dat	Nemunas/Verkne_Vebyksles
Nemunas/Nemunas	22i.dat	Nemunas/Perseke
Nemunas/Nemunas	25i.dat	Merkys/Merkys
Nemunas/Nemunas	29i.dat	Nemunas/Baltoji
Nemunas/Nemunas	31i.dat	Jura/Jura_Gals
Nemunas/Nemunas	32i.dat	Nemunas/Sysa_Silute
Nemunas/Nemunas	6i.dat	Nemunas/Gege
Nemunas/Streva_ecl_semeliskes	7i.dat	Nemunas/Streva
Nemunelis/Nemunelis_LT	3i.dat	Nemunelis/Apasciai
Neris/Neris_upe	10i.dat	Zeimena/Zeimena
Neris/Neris_upe	16i.dat	Neris/Voke
Neris/Neris_upe	18i.dat	Neris/Vilnia
Neris/Neris_upe	1i.dat	Shventoji/Shventoji_K
Neris/Neris_upe	5i.dat	Neris/Muse
Nevezis/Nevezis	10i.dat	Nevezis/Smilga
Nevezis/Nevezis	11i.dat	Nevezis/Obelis
Nevezis/Nevezis	12i.dat	Nevezis/Barupe
Nevezis/Nevezis	13i.dat	Nevezis/Susve
Nevezis/Nevezis	14i.dat	Nevezis/Aluona
Nevezis/Nevezis	3i.dat	Nevezis/Panevezis
Nevezis/Nevezis	4i.dat	Nevezis/Kirstina
Nevezis/Nevezis	5i.dat	Nevezis/Upyte
Parejais/Pareja_Akmene	3i.dat	Parejais/Kretinga
Sesupe/Sesupe	3i.dat	Sesupe/Nova
Sesupe/Sesupe	5i.dat	Sesupe/Sirvinta
Sesupe/Sesupe	6i.dat	Sesupe/Viskakis1
Sesupe/Sesupe	7i.dat	Sesupe/Sesupe_upst
Sesupe/Sesupe	7i.dat	Sesupe/Pilve
Shventoji/Shventoji_K	10i.dat	Shventoji/Sierastis
Shventoji/Shventoji_K	14i.dat	Shventoji/Sirvinta
Shventoji/Shventoji_K	2i.dat	Shventoji/Jara
Shventoji/Shventoji_K	3i.dat	Shventoji/Shventoji_A
Shventoji/Shventoji_K	3i.dat	Shventoji/Vyzuona
Shventoji/Shventoji_K	8i.dat	Shventoji/Suraiza
Venta/Venta	3i.dat	Venta/Uogys
Venta/Venta	6i.dat	Venta/Virvyčia
Venta/Venta	7i.dat	Venta/Dabikina
Zeimena/Zeimena	1i.dat	Zeimena/Kaltena
Zeimena/Zeimena	1i.dat	Zeimena/Dumble1
Zeimena/Zeimena	3i.dat	Zeimena/Lakaja
Zeimena/Zeimena	6i.dat	Zeimena/Stirnele

The entire modeling system (see structure of folders and files in Section 4.2) contains the data used for preparation of the model setups, the means for this preparation, the setups itself as well as precalculated results of the water quality modeling system for the time period 2000-2010.

4.2. Structure of folders and files

The structure of the folders and files of the modelling system is as follows, see also Fig. 22:

Fig. 22. Folder and file structure of the modelling system.

1. The **root** folder (or folder **Lietuva**) contains the folders of the modelling system components and the following files:
 - a. Batch file **all.bat** for performing sequential calculations of all setups of the water quality modelling system/
 - b. Other **batch files** which are invoked by **all.bat**.
 - c. Executable **swat2009_paic.exe** – the modified SWAT2009 solver.
 - d. Executable **UpdateInlets.exe** – the program going through the setups and copying the outlet results of appropriate setups to the inlet data for downstream setups. It uses the connection definition file **Baseini_konekcijas.txt** from folder **Tabulas**.
 - e. If the PAICSWAT software PAIC (2012) is installed – the executable **paicswat.exe** and configuration file **paicswat.ini**.
2. 19 folders **region/setup** (according to the 3rd column of Table 12 contain the further file and folder structure of the SWAT setup of particular watershed (including the calculation results if any).
3. The **Script** folder contains the scripts summarised in Section 4.3.
4. Folder **Data** contains the following information (in alphabetical order):

- a. Shape file **all.shp** containing information on the melioration used by **updateDrainage.py**.
 - b. Shape files **atm_depos_poly_y2005_totNOx.shp**, **atm_depos_poly_y2005_totNHx.shp** and **atm_depos_poly_y2005_prec.shp** contain Information about atmospheric deposition, used by **atmosphericDeposition.py**.
 - c. **Baseinu_global_saistibas_simplify.shp** is a shape file describing the connections between subbasins globally. It is used by PAICSWAT, PAIC (2012).
 - d. Shape file **BasinGCS.shp** contains information about precipitation corrections in subbasins, it is used by **precipitationCorrection.py**.
 - e. Shape file **counties_2004.shp** contains information about mineral and organic fertilizers in county level, used by **UpdateManagement.py**.
 - f. Shape file **Lakes_and_ponds_for_modelling.shp** contains information about lakes and ponds used by **updateLakes.py**.
 - g. Shape file **nodes.shp** contains points and information about the river node points used by PAICSWAT, PAIC (2012).
 - h. Shape file **Point_source.shp** contains information about point sources and their loads used by **updatePointSources.py**.
 - i. Shape file **Reservoirs_with_parameters.shp** contains information about reservoirs, used by **updateReservoirs.py**.
 - j. Shape file **stations_vs_real.shp** contains information about relations between subbasins and weather stations; it used by **precipitationCorrection.py**.
 - k. Database **statpcp.dbf** contains information about precipitation stations, used by **precipitationCorrection.py**.
 - l. **SWAT2005_2.mdb** is the SWAT2005 database updated with the appropriate SOIL types.
 - m. **transb.dbf** is temporary file used by **transboundary.py**.
 - n. Shape file **transboundary.shp** contains information about transboundary subbasins and their area used by **transboundary.py**.
 - o. Shape file **upes.shp** contains the river lines used by PAICSWAT software, PAIC (2012).
5. Folder **Tabulas** contains
- a. File **augsnes.xls** contains information about used SOIL parameters. This file is not used by programs.
 - b. File **Baseini_konekcijas.txt** contains information of connections between

SWAT setups, used by both **updateInlets.py** and executable **updateInlets.exe** (called also for by **all.bat**).

- c. File **coefficients.txt** is a table of the regionalized SWAT parameters used for their application to the setups. It contains a list of parameters, regions and values. File is used by **updateCoefficients.py**.
- d. **Crop_PHU.xlsx** is a table of PHU for all crops. It is included only for information and is not used by scripts.
- e. **HWSD.mdb** is harmonized World soil database. It is included just as a reference.
- f. Excel file **Koeficienti_baseini.xls** contains a table from which an ASCII file **coefficients.txt** is created.

6. Folder **Observations** contains

- a. Files **Nemunas_load.txt** and **Neris_load.txt** are the transboundary inlet time series. These files are only for information.
- b. ASCII files **QObs.txt** and **QObs.sta** are, respectively, discharge observation data file and station list. Both files are used by
 - i. PAICSWAT software PAIC (2012) for the visualisation of data and analysis of calculation results.
 - ii. Python script **transBoundaryinlets.py** for creating Nemunas and Neris transboundary inlet.
- c. **QStations.xlsx** is a table from which **QStations.sta** is created (for information only).
- d. ASCII files **weatherdata.txt** and **weatherdata.sta** are, respectively, the meteorological observation data file and station list. Both files are used by **MDB2SWAT.py** for creating weather time series.
- e. ASCII files **WQObs.txt** and **WQObs.sta** are, respectively, water quality observation data file and station list. Both files are used by
 - i. PAICSWAT software PAIC (2012) for the visualisation of data and analysis of calculation results.
 - ii. Python script **transBoundaryinlets.py** for creating Nemunas and Neris transboundary inlet time series.

4.3. Python scripts

The Python scripts (folder **Scripts**) supplied with the water quality modeling system are listed in this section in alphabetical order and divided into 4 groups. The reference to particular scripts may be given throughout the User manual.

1. Scripts for **the update of the ArcSWAT setups** i.e. for filling the geodatabase
 - a. **atmosphericDeposition.py**. This procedure applies atmospheric deposition to ArcSWAT geodatabase file as concentration of nitrogen in rainfall, by intersecting deposition shape files **atm_depos_poly_y2005_totNOx.shp**, **atm_depos_poly_y2005_totNHx.shp** and **atm_depos_poly_y2005_prec.shp** with given setup.
 - b. **precipitationCorrection.py**. This procedure implements precipitation correction and updates the geodatabase accordingly. It uses the shape files **BasinGCS.shp**, **stations_vs_real.shp** and database **statpcp.dbf**.
 - c. **transboundary.py**. The procedure links transboundary areas of the watersheds from shape file **transboundary.shp** to the model setups.
 - d. **transBoundaryInlets.py**. Creates transboundary inlets in the setups using ASCII files **QObs.sta**, **QObs.txt**, **WQObs.sta** and **WQObs.txt**.
 - e. **updateDrainage.py**. This procedure creates tile drainage information in setup geodatabase, by intersecting drainage data from **all.shp** with the setup.
 - f. **updateInlets.py**. Creates the [dummy] inlets for the setups which require external inlets using information in file **Baseini_konekcijas.txt**.
 - f. **updateLakes.py**. The procedure intersects lake and pond information from shape file **Lakes_and_ponds_for_modelling.shp** with the setups and updates geodatabase. After that the accounting for lakes is disabled.
 - g. **updateManagement.py**. This procedure applies agricultural management operations to ArcSWAT geodatabase, including mineral fertilizer application, organic fertilizer application by animals and animal grazing. It uses shape file **counties_2004.shp**.
 - h. **updatePndResAreas.py**. The procedure subtracts the lake, pond and reservoir areas from the subbasin area to avoid double accounting.
 - i. **updatePointSources.py**. The procedure intersects point sources data from the shape file **Point_source.shp** with setups and fills the pollution time series into geodatabase.
 - j. **updateReservoirs.py**. The procedure intersects the river network with reservoir information from shape file **Reservoirs_with_parameters.shp** and creates reservoirs for setups, fills the geodatabase with the parameters needed for reservoirs.
 - k. **updateWetlands.py**. This procedure updates wetlands in the setup, depending on the size of territory with the landuse characteristic for wetlands.

2. The scripts related to **update of SWAT coefficients and settings**.
 - a. **changeCoefficients.py**. The procedure changes the ArcSWAT calculation coefficients in the geodatabase file. It invokes the scripts **changeSoilCoefs.py** and **changeMGT1Coefs**.
 - b. **changeMGT1Coefs.py**. The procedure updates the management coefficients in the ArcSWAT geodatabase.
 - c. **changeSoilCoefs.py**. The procedure updates soil related calculation coefficients in the ArcSWAT geodatabase..
 - d. **defineSimulationPeriod.py**. Defines the simulation period and the time step for the output of results in the geodatabase according to the settings in **settings.py**
 - e. **updateCoefficients.py**. The procedure updates all SWAT coefficient values which are different from the default values in database **SWAT2005_2.mdb**. It uses the regionalized coefficient list in file **coefficients.txt**. The procedure invokes **changeCoefficients.py**, **changeMGT1Coefs.py** and **changeSoilCoefs.py** as necessary..
3. The scripts which allow for the **automated generation of the modeling system setups** – update of ArcSWAT geodatabases (of all setups) and creation of all SWAT setups from all ArcSWAT setups.
 - a. **copyMDBSetups.py**. Copies all (or specified) model setups from folder **root_dir_from** to **root_dir_to** and creates appropriate directory structure.
 - b. **MDB2SWAT.py**. The procedure screates SWAT setup (files) from the ArcSWAT MDB geodatabase. It also fills the weather data into SWAT setups from the ASCII files **weatherdata.sta** and **weatherdata.txt**.
 - c. **precipitationCorrection.py** is the Python procedure of implementing precipitation correction in ArcSWAT geodatabase. It uses shape files **stations_vs_real.shp**, **statpcp.shp** and **BasinGCS.shp**
 - d. **updateAll.py**. Applies all actions to update one ArcSWAT setup, invokes appropriate procedures from script groups 1 and 2 above.
 - e. **Main.py**. Runs python initialisation procedures (script group 4) and reads setup list from **settings.py**. Copies setups to new directory invoking **copyMDBSetups.py** (if needed). Iterates through all setups running **updateAll.py**. Script is invoked for updating setups and it is the one which is run when **run.bat** from the root directory is started.
 - f. **Settings.py**. Procedure which defines the configuration of the modeling system, lists all needed files for all scripts and determines which input data values from which files are used. This script contains settings for all other scripts.
4. The Python scripts which are different **utilities** (subroutines of other scripts). These scripts are not designed for invoking by user.
 - a. **accessLnk.py**. Initialises Microsoft Access link.

- b. **arconn.py**. Initialises ArcGis scripting link.
- c. **arcSWATConnection.py**. Initialises ArcSWAT link.
- d. **linkTables.py**. Links tables in ArcGIS.
- e. **makeSetups.py**. Enables going through all geodatabases in setups.
- f. **mdbLink.py**. Links tables in Microsoft Access.
- g. **RunExe.py**. Enables Python to run executables from Python scripts.
- h. **setupInitialActions.py**. Sets up the initial actions needed to run other scripts.
- i. **setupUtils.py**. Collection of useful functions and subroutines necessary for the processing of ArcSWAT setups.

Two batch files are prepared for running **main.py**: **run.bat** runs interpreter version Python v.2.4 (installed with ArcMAP v.9.2) while **run10.bat** runs interpreter version Python v.2.6 (installed with ArcMAP v.10.0).

The script files are located within the modeling system, see the structure of folders and files in Section 4.2 and Fig.22. They may be located elsewhere due to the location of modeling system folders and files is defined in **settings.py**.

4.4. Running and updating modeling system

Let us consider the most important operations by the modeling system.

Running the single setup

1. The model of any of the watersheds of the first hierarchical level (Table 13) can be run independently. It can be done by two methods:
 - a. Copying the **swat2009_paic.exe** to the appropriate setup and running it.
 - b. Alternatively – by PAICSWAT software (PAIC2012), if installed.
2. The model of any of watersheds of the higher hierarchical levels (Table 13) can be run if the upstream watersheds (of lower hierarchical levels) are calculated in advance. The needed upstream watershed can be detected from Tables 13-14.
3. After calculation of the upstream watersheds the program **UpdateInlets.exe** must be run for automated copying the calculated SWAT outflows of the upstream catchments to the downstream setup directories.

Running the modeling system

1. The whole modeling system may be calculated by the batch file **all.bat** which performs all necessary operations: calculating the 1st hierarchical level, updating inlets, calculating the 2nd hierarchical level, updating inlets, calculating the 3rd hierarchical level, updating inlets and calculating the 4th hierarchical level.
2. The setups in different hierarchical levels (Section 4.1, Figure 21, Table 13) 1 to 4 can be calculated separately by batch files **all_lev_l1_c1.bat**, **all_lev_l1_c1.bat**, **all_lev_l1_c1.bat**, **all_lev_l1_c1.bat**.
3. The default (precalculated) calculation results are for 11 year period from 2000 to 2010 with daily output of results. The default calculation settings (in all ArcSWAT and SWAT setups and **settings.py**) assume calculation for time period 1997-2010 and daily output of results. The first three years of the model run are a warm-up period and are not written in the output files. User may change both the calculation period and the frequency of output results in **settings.py** and update them in setups with **defineSimulationPeriod.py**.

Updating the model and its input data.

The modeling system contains all data used for its building. Therefore – in general – we recommend to change the initial data and rebuild the system at some level instead of changing setups itself. Thus, the changing model data can be done by the same means which are used for building the modeling system. Updating the model data may be done at various levels.

1. **Changing the data related to the raw setups** (Section 3.1). These data are generally changed outside the modeling system. The application of changes requires running the steps of preparation of raw model setups (Section 3.2) and preparation of initial model setups (Section 3.3).

2. **Changing the data related to the initial setups** (Section 3.3). The Section 3.3 contains a reference to the scripts which is used for particular data operation. We recommend to perform changing the respective initial data and (if needed) **Settings.py** file and run the automated update of all ArcSWAT and SWAT setups – **main.py** (or **run.bat**).
3. **Manual changing of data** in particular setup can be done. This is recommended for minor changes, test and parameter studies. However user should be cautious due to changes introduced at this level will be override by the default configuration in **settings.py** the next time **main.py** will be invoked. Therefore user must implemented the selected useful changes also in the raw data (incl. parameters). The possibilities of changing particular setups are
 - a. At ArcSWAT setup by ArcSWAT means. After this operation **MDB2SWAT.py** must be run to create a corresponding SWAT setup.
 - b. At SWAT setup either by SWAT means or PAICSWAT software PAIC (2012) if available.

4.5. Model parameters (calibrated coefficients)

The calibration and validation of the particular setups of the water quality modeling system are considered in PAIC & ELLE (2012 a-c).

In this Section we include the full table of calibration parameters. According to PAIC & ELLE (2012c) the are regionalised in 19 groups. The set of regionalised SWAT co-efficients after calibration are summarised in Table 15. The values expressed as “%” indicate the difference from the default coefficient value in the SWAT database **SWAT2005_2.mdb**. Table 15 contains indicative regional values of the coefficients – the calibrated coefficient values are supplied electronically with the water quality modelling system (file **coefficients.txt**) in folder “Tabulas”.

Table 15. The values of the calibration parameters for 19 regions.

Table	Coefficient	Bartuva	Dauguva	Dubysa	Jura	Lielupe_MI	Merkys
BSN	CDN	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02
BSN	CMN	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
BSN	DEPIMP_BSN	0	0	0	0	0	3000
BSN	NPERCO	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134
BSN	RSDCO	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035
BSN	SDNCO	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9	1,05	0,9
BSN	SFTMP	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
BSN	SMFMN	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	3
BSN	SMFMX	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	3
BSN	SMTMP	1	1	1	1	1	2
BSN	SPCON	0,00002	0,00004	0,0001	0,0004	0,00001	0,0001
BSN	SPEXP	2	1	1	1	3	1
BSN	SURLAG	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32
BSN	TIMP	1	1	1	1	1	0,1
GW	ALPHA_BF	0,08	0,07	0,06	0,05	0,1	0,005
GW	GW_DELAY	0,3	0,3	2	0,3	0,3	60
GW	GW_REVAP	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,12
GW	GWQMN	100	100	100	100	100	100
GW	HLIFE_NGW	20	25	30	20	50	15
GW	RCHRG_DP	0,01	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05
GW	REVAPMN	125	125	125	150	125	125
HRU	CANMX	5	10	10	15	10	10
HRU	ESCO	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
HRU	LAT_TTIME	0	0	0	0	0	3
HRU	OV_N	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14
MGT	CN2	-24%	-15%	-15%	-15%	-15%	-15%
RTE	CH_COV	1	1	1	1	1	1
RTE	CH_EROD	0	0	0	0	0	0
RTE	CH_N2	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06
SOL	SOL_AWC1	-5%	-9%	30%	30%	44%	30%

SOL	SOL_AWC2	-5%	-9%	30%	30%	44%	30%
SOL	SOL_K1	500%	500%	500%	500%	462%	500%
SOL	SOL_K2	500%	500%	500%	500%	462%	500%
SOL	USLE_K1	-50%	-96%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SOL	USLE_K2	-50%	-96%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SWQ	BC1	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55
SWQ	BC2	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1
SWQ	BC3	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21
SWQ	BC4	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2
SWQ	RK1	0,01	0,01	0,25	0,15	0,25	0,25
SWQ	RK2	2,5	2,5	2,5	0,5	1,5	2,5
SWQ	RK3	0,15	0,01	0,25	0,25	0,12	0,25
SWQ	RS1	1	1	1	1	1	1
SWQ	RS2	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
SWQ	RS3	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
SWQ	RS4	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05
SWQ	RS5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5

Table 15 (continued). The values of the calibration parameters for 19 regions.

Table	Coefficient	Minija	Musa	Nemunas	Nemunelis	Neris	Nevezis	Parejais
BSN	CDN	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02
BSN	CMN	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
BSN	DEPIMP_BSN	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BSN	NPERCO	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134
BSN	RSDCO	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035
BSN	SDNCO	0,9	1	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,95	0,9
BSN	SFTMP	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
BSN	SMFMN	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	3	4,5	4,5
BSN	SMFMX	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	3	4,5	4,5
BSN	SMTMP	1	1	1	1	1,4	1	1
BSN	SPCON	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001
BSN	SPEXP	2	2,5	1	1	1	1	1
BSN	SURLAG	0,5	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32
BSN	TIMP	1	1	1	1	0,1	1	1
GW	ALPHA_BF	0,2	0,07	0,07	0,07	0,05	0,07	0,07
GW	GW_DELAY	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	10	0,3	0,3
GW	GW_REVAP	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02
GW	GWQMN	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
GW	H LIFE_NGW	20	30	25	50	18	40	35
GW	RCHRG_DP	0,05	0	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,09	0,05
GW	REVAPMN	125	125	125	125	125	125	125
HRU	CANMX	15	10	10	10	10	15	10
HRU	ESCO	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
HRU	LAT_TTIME	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

HRU	OV_N	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14
MGT	CN2	-25%	-24%	-15%	-15%	-15%	-19%	-15%
RTE	CH_COV	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
RTE	CH_EROD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
RTE	CH_N2	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06
SOL	SOL_AWC1	56%	0%	30%	30%	30%	27%	30%
SOL	SOL_AWC2	56%	0%	30%	30%	30%	27%	30%
SOL	SOL_K1	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%
SOL	SOL_K2	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%
SOL	USLE_K1	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SOL	USLE_K2	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SWQ	BC1	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55
SWQ	BC2	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1
SWQ	BC3	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21
SWQ	BC4	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,23
SWQ	RK1	0,03	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25
SWQ	RK2	2,5	0,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5
SWQ	RK3	0,03	0,2	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25
SWQ	RS1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
SWQ	RS2	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
SWQ	RS3	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
SWQ	RS4	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05
SWQ	RS5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,05

Table 15 (continued). The values of the calibration parameters for 19 regions.

Table	Coefficient	Prieglius	Sesupe	Shventoji	Sveentoji	Venta	Zeimena
BSN	CDN	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02
BSN	CMN	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
BSN	DEPIMP_BSN	0	0	0	0	0	8000
BSN	NPERCO	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134	0,134
BSN	RSDCO	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035	0,035
BSN	SDNCO	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9
BSN	SFTMP	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
BSN	SMFMN	4,5	4,5	4,5	3	4,5	3
BSN	SMFMX	4,5	4,5	4,5	3	4,5	3
BSN	SMTMP	1	1	1	1,5	1	2
BSN	SPCON	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001
BSN	SPEXP	1	1	2	1	1	1
BSN	SURLAG	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32	0,32
BSN	TIMP	1	1	1	0,1	1	0,1
GW	ALPHA_BF	0,07	0,07	0,04	0,06	0,07	0,03
GW	GW_DELAY	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	30
GW	GW_REVAP	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,12
GW	GWQMN	100	100	100	100	100	100

GW	HLIFE_NGW	20	30	50	25	25	10
GW	RCHRG_DP	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,35
GW	REVAPMN	125	125	125	125	125	125
HRU	CANMX	10	10	20	10	10	10
HRU	ESCO	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
HRU	LAT_TTIME	0	0	0	0	0	3
HRU	OV_N	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14
MGT	CN2	-15%	-15%	-30%	-15%	-15%	-15%
RTE	CH_COV	1	1	1	1	1	1
RTE	CH_EROD	0	0	0	0	0	0
RTE	CH_N2	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06
SOL	SOL_AWC1	30%	30%	57%	30%	30%	30%
SOL	SOL_AWC2	30%	30%	57%	30%	30%	30%
SOL	SOL_K1	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%
SOL	SOL_K2	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%	500%
SOL	USLE_K1	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SOL	USLE_K2	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
SWQ	BC1	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55	0,55
SWQ	BC2	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1
SWQ	BC3	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21
SWQ	BC4	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2
SWQ	RK1	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25
SWQ	RK2	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5
SWQ	RK3	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25
SWQ	RS1	1	1	1	1	1	1
SWQ	RS2	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
SWQ	RS3	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01
SWQ	RS4	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05
SWQ	RS5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5

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